

Craters in Maps given by Spaceborne Digital Elevation Models

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Abstract: In the proposed discussion we stress the possibility to use maps from Spaceborne Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) to analyse the topography of craters or crater-like structures. The Digital Elevation Model here used is that proposed by Yamazaki, Ikeshima, Tawatari, Yamaguchi, O'Loughlin, Neal, Sampson, Kanae and Bates, in the Geophysical Research Letters, 2017, and implemented at the web site it-ch.topographic-map.com. Crater-like structures can be observed in visible satellite images, but elevation profiles are fundamental to understand their geological nature. Here we will show that the DEM maps are able to easily evidence the elevation features, giving the possibility of a first remote analysis of them.

Keywords: Craters, Spaceborne Digital Elevation Models, Google Earth, Satellite imagery. Libya, Sudan, Nuclear Craters.

Torino, March 11, 2022

In the past, I have proposed some methods to enhance the visibility of features in the satellite images of Google Maps [1],[2], to find the presence of crater-like structures in them. Once a crater has been located in the visible satellite images of Google Maps for instance, or in those of the more performing Google Earth Pro software, it is necessary to characterize its structure by means of elevation profiles. We could use the corresponding terrain maps given by the same Google Maps or the elevation profiles provided by Google Earth. However, today, we have the possibility to use a Spaceborne Digital Elevation Model (DEM) to determine, of the detected crater-like structure, the related topography in detailed colour maps. Here, we will use the colour maps coming from a DEM proposed in [3], and implemented by the web site <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>.

Let us report some words from the abstract of the article by Yamazaki et al., 2017 [3]. "Spaceborne digital elevation models (DEMs) are fundamental input for many geoscience studies, but they still include nonnegligible height errors. [In Yamazaki et al., 2017, the researchers] introduce a high-accuracy global DEM at 3" resolution (~90 m at the equator) by eliminating major error components from existing DEMs. [They] separated absolute bias, stripe noise, speckle noise, and tree height bias using multiple satellite data sets and filtering techniques. After the error removal, land areas mapped with ± 2 m or better vertical accuracy were increased from 39% to 58%. Significant improvements were found in flat regions where height errors larger than topography variability, and landscapes such as river networks and hill-valley structures, became clearly represented. ... The newly developed DEM will enhance many geoscience applications which are terrain dependent" [3].

Of course, the DEM proposed in [3] is proper for studies of geoscience. However, it is also useful for investigating local landscapes, and some applications have been previously proposed, for instance, in [4],[5],[6] and [7]. Here, we will apply the model [3] to craters, those shown in [1] and [2], and several others. We can use the web site <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>, having, as in the

previously proposed discussions [4-7], excellent results.

First, let me express many thanks to Yamazaki D., D. Ikeshima, R. Tawatari, T. Yamaguchi, F. O'Loughlin, J.C. Neal, C.C. Sampson, S. Kanae & P.D. Bates (Yamazaki et al., 2017), for their fundamental work on digital elevation data and models, and many thanks to the excellent web site at link <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com> which is fundamental for the maps.

A crater in Northern Sudan?

Let us start from Ref. [1]. In [1], I discussed the use of a wavelet filter for a processing of Google satellite imagery. The wavelet filter is a tool included in a freely downloadable software (Iris), well-known for the processing of astronomical images. Combining the image obtained after applying the wavelet filter, with an image created with GIMP and AstroFracTool software [8], the visibility of the landforms, as obtained from Google Maps, is strongly increased.

One of the example proposed in [1] is a crater in Sudan, near the Nile. In the Fig. 2 of [1], this crater is shown. The River Nile has several bends where it is changing its flowing direction. One bend is at 19.937N,30.296E. Before the bend, from the river departs a small branch, which creates the Arduan island. Few kilometres N-W from this island, there is a crater-like landform, with a diameter of 2.5 km. Here, in the Figure 1, the reader can see the pin giving the location of the crater. Activating the “Gallery” in Google Earth Pro, we can see the following information: “New Crater? By: PedroPabloBarralMartin, Date: 2006-08-12”. The structure is indicated as a possible meteoric impact crater. In en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_impact_craters_in_Africa, this crater is also indicated as a possible impact structure, and named as “Mahas”, from the name of the local population.

Fig.1 : The pin S0 indicates the location of a crater near the Nile in Northern Sudan (20° 1' 53" N, 30° 13' 48" E or 20.03 30.23). Many thanks to Google Earth Pro.

Fig.2 : The crater (Northern Sudan, 20° 1' 53" N, 30° 13' 48" E) in a map provided by the web site <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>. Many thanks to Yamazaki D., D. Ikeshima, R. Tawatari, T. Yamaguchi, F. O'Loughlin, J.C. Neal, C.C. Sampson, S. Kanae & P.D. Bates, 2017, for their fundamental work on digital elevation data and models, and many thanks to the excellent web site, which is fundamental for the maps.

Fig.3 : The crater (Northern Sudan, 20° 1' 53" N, 30° 13' 48" E) in another map provided by the web site <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>.

In the Figures 2 and 3, we can see two elevation maps from the web site <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>. The crater is that shown in [1] (Northern Sudan, 20° 1' 53" N, 30° 13' 48" E). Is this an impact crater? It seems so.

Fig.4 : The same crater of the Figure 3, with a satellite image as a background. The map provided by the web site <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com> can have several layouts. It is possible to select OpenStreetMap, Open TopoMap, Carto / Light, Carto / Topo, CyclOSM, and, as in this case, Esri / Imagery. By clicking on the map it is possible to display elevation of a specific location.

Fig. 5: An elevation profile obtained by means of Google Earth (many thanks to Google).

In the Figure 5, it is shown an elevation profile that we can obtain by means of Google Earth. The crater is that shown in the Figure 2, 3 and 4 (Northern Sudan, 20° 1' 53" N, 30° 13' 48" E). The profile is corresponding to the red segment on the satellite image. It is clear that, to have a complete view, it is necessary to have several of these profiles. A map is more convenient.

Fig. 6 – On the left, the Google Earth Pro image of a crater-like structure in Sudan (19.213 N, 35.983), mentioned in Ref. [9]. Other similar structures are given in [9] On the right, the corresponding DEM map from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

In the following image, another crater-like structure in Sudan, not given in [9].

Fig. 7 – On the left, the Google Earth Pro image of a crater-like structure in Sudan (17°57' N, 37°55'E). On the right, the corresponding DEM map from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

Craters in Africa and Arab World

Ref. [10] is an article entitled “Impact structures in Africa: A review”. The authors, Wolf Uwe Reimold and Christian Koeberl, are dedicating the review to their “students, collaborators and friends in Africa, without whose support we could not have successfully pursued our investigations of confirmed and possible African impact structures”. Highlights of [10] tell that the review is giving 1) a comprehensive review of confirmed, proposed and disproven impact structures, 2) a general introduction to impact cratering science and to accepted recognition criteria for impact craters, and 3) a comprehensive bibliography on impact structures and related studies in Africa.

In the Ref. [11], entitled “Meteorite Impact Structures in the Arab World: An Overview”, the author, Moulley Charaf Chabou, provides a “review about confirmed, proposed, and disproven meteorite impact structures in the Arab countries. Among the ~190 confirmed impact structures/sites on Earth, only 13 have been identified in the countries of the Arab world: Agoudal (Morocco), Amguid (Algeria), Aouelloul (Mauritania), BP (Libya), Kamil (Egypt), Oasis (Libya), Ouarkiz (Algeria), Jebel Waqf as Suwwan (Jordan), Saqqar (Saudi Arabia), Talemzane (Algeria), Tenoumer (Mauritania), Tin Bider (Algeria), and Wabar (Saudi Arabia). Thirty-three other structures of alleged impact origin and located in the Arab countries have been proposed in the literature. Based on the examination of satellite images and available field geologic, petrographic, and geochemical documentation, some of these proposed features are not of impact origin. ... Field investigations, including the collection and analyses of rock samples, are required for adding new candidates to the list of confirmed impact craters in the Arab countries” [11]. The abstract is stressing that the “only criteria that prove evidence for an impact origin of circular geological structures are the occurrence of shock-metamorphic effects in the target rocks (shatter cones and diagnostic shock-metamorphic mineral deformation and transformation phenomena), the discovery of preserved meteorite fragments, or detection of geochemical traces of meteoritic projectiles” [11].

Identifying impact craters (Wikipedia)

From https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Impact_crater

“Non-explosive volcanic craters can usually be distinguished from impact craters by their irregular shape and the association of volcanic flows and other volcanic materials. Impact craters produce melted rocks as well, but usually in smaller volumes with different characteristics.[12] The distinctive mark of an impact crater is the presence of rock that has undergone shock-metamorphic effects, such as shatter cones, melted rocks, and crystal deformations. The problem is that these materials tend to be deeply buried, at least for simple craters. They tend to be revealed in the uplifted center of a complex crater, however.” [13][14].

The impacts are producing distinctive shock-metamorphic effects, allowing impact sites to be identified. Such shock-metamorphic effects can include [15]:

- 1) A layer of "brecciated" rock under the floor of the crater. The layer is known as the "breccia lens".
- 2) Shatter cones, which are formed most easily in fine-grained rocks.
- 3) High-temperature rock types, including laminated and welded blocks of sand, spherulites and tektites, or glassy spatters of molten rock. Wikipedia notes that “The impact origin of tektites has been questioned by some researchers; they have observed some volcanic features in tektites not found in impactites. ... While rocks melted by the impact resemble volcanic rocks, they incorporate unmelted fragments of bedrock, form unusually large and unbroken fields, and have a much more mixed chemical composition than volcanic materials spewed up from within the Earth. They also may have relatively large amounts of trace elements that are associated with meteorites, such as nickel, platinum, iridium, and cobalt”.
- 4) Microscopic pressure deformations of minerals. “These include fracture patterns in crystals of quartz and feldspar, and formation of high-pressure materials such as diamond, derived from graphite and other carbon compounds, or stishovite and coesite, varieties of shocked quartz”.
- 5) The buried craters can be identified through drill coring, aerial electromagnetic resistivity imaging, and airborne gravity gradiometry.”

In the Libyan Desert

In [2], I proposed a survey of a region of the Libyan desert, south of the Waha oil field and south-east of the Sarir oil field, using the satellite images from Google Maps. The images revealed several crater-like landforms, which could be subsidence or, perhaps, impact craters. “During a survey with Google Maps, to observe the Great Man-Made River, south of the Waha oil field and south-east of the Sarir oil field, I observed some crater-like landforms” [2]. The Figures given in [2] are proposed after a processing to enhance their visibility. “These structures could be some subsidence craters, created as the roof of a cavity collapses, causing the surface to depress”. Details on the oil fields are given by Wikipedia at the two following links: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Waha_field and http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sarir_field.

In the Figure 8, the reader can see the pins giving the location of the crater-like structures in Libya. Activating the “Gallery” in Google Earth Pro, we can see the following information: “Crater Chain - By: billyboblennon - Date: 2006-04-19 - Very possibly impact craters”.

Again, are the structures in Libya some crater impacts? In particular, is it a chain of craters? Let us use again the DEMs from [3].

Fig.8 : The pins indicate the location of crater-like structures in the Libya Desert. Many thanks to Google Earth Pro.

Fig. 9 - The region of the pins in Fig. 8, in a map provided by the web site <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>. Many thanks again to Yamazaki D., D. Ikeshima, R. Tawatari, T. Yamaguchi, F. O'Loughlin, J.C. Neal, C.C. Sampson, S. Kanae & P.D. Bates, 2017, for their fundamental work on digital elevation data and models, and many thanks to the excellent web site, which is fundamental for the maps.

Fig. 10: The elevation map of the area where pins L0 and L1 of the Figure 8 are located.

Fig. 11: Pins L0 and L1 of the Figure 8. Diameters are of about 1.5 and 1.2 km.

Fig. 12: Pin L2 of the Figure 7.

Fig. 13: Pin L3 of the Figure 7.

Then, let us consider now the DEM maps of confirmed impact craters.

Oasis Crater

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Oasis_crater

“Oasis is a meteorite crater in Libya. The crater is exposed at the surface, and has been significantly eroded. The prominent topographic ring is only the central uplift, which is about 5.2 km (~3 miles) in diameter, while the original crater rim is estimated to have been 18 km (~11 miles) in diameter. The age is estimated to be less than 120 million years (Lower Cretaceous).” [16],[17]

Fig.14 : The Oasis Crater (24° 34' 28" N, 24° 24' 37" E) in a map provided by the web site <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>.

Aorounga Crater

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aorounga_crater

“Aorounga is an eroded meteorite impact crater in Chad, Africa. The exposed remnant of the crater is 12.6 km (7.8 mi) in diameter and its age is estimated to be less than 345 million years (Carboniferous or younger). An outer and an inner ring (11 and 7 km, respectively) rise about 100 m above the mean level of the surrounding plain (see topographic map). Both aforementioned rings are separated by a relatively flat depression of uniform width. A possible central hill, maybe an uplift structure, of 1.5 km is almost centrally located in the depression. The crater is accompanied by two nearby circular features revealed by Space Shuttle SIR-C radar. These may be related impact craters, and if correct, Aorounga may be part of a crater chain. On the assumption that this hypothesis is correct, the exposed Aorounga crater is sometimes referred to as Aorounga South. The central highland, or peak, of the crater is surrounded by a small sand-filled trough; this in turn is surrounded by a larger circular trough. Linear rock ridges alternating with light orange sand deposits cross the image from upper left to lower right; these are called yardangs by geomorphologists. Yardangs form by wind erosion of exposed rock layers in a unidirectional wind field. The wind blows from the north-east at Aorounga, and sand dunes formed between the yardangs are actively migrating to the south-west.” [18],[19],[20],[21],[22],[23],[24],[25],[26]

Fig. 15 – Aorounga Impact Crater.

Let us consider the link https://www.boulder.swri.edu/~bottke/crater_chain/chain.html. The author, Bill Bottke, tells: “A second study using radar imagery of the 17 km diameter, 360 Myr old Aorounga impact crater in northern Chad discovered a ~10 km wide circular structure adjacent to the Aorounga crater and a second, less distinct feature somewhat displaced from the line defined by

the other two (S.C. Ocampo and K.O. Pope (1996) Lunar Planet. Sci. XXVII p. 977). Field work to verify that the new structures are impact craters has not been attempted, but it is possible that they and Aorounga are members of a crater chain.”

The article by Ocampo and Pope [25], as told by Bottke, is proposing four impact craters. In the SIR-C L band imagery, the craters are given by concentric circular or semi-circular troughs. In the following image, the locations of three of them are given in satellite maps.

Fig. 16 – On the right, three of the Aorounga craters in the Google Earth Pro image. On the left, the corresponding DEM map from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

Fig. 17 a – The Quarkziz Crater in DEM maps from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

Fig. 17 b – The Quarkziz Crater in DEM maps from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

In Algeria

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ouarkiz_crater

“Ouarkziz is a meteorite impact crater in Algeria. It is 3.5 kilometers in diameter and the age is estimated to be less than 70 million years (Cretaceous or younger). The crater is exposed at the surface. The Ouarkziz Impact Crater is located in northwestern Algeria, close to the border with Morocco. The crater was formed by a meteor impact less than 70 million years ago, during the late Cretaceous Period of the Mesozoic Era. Originally called Tindouf, the 3.5-kilometer wide crater has been heavily eroded since its formation; however, its circular morphology is highlighted by exposures of older sedimentary rock layers that form roughly northwest to southeast-trending ridgelines. From the vantage point of an astronaut on the International Space Station, the impact crater is clearly visible with a magnifying camera lens. A geologist interpreting this image to build a geological history of the region would conclude that the Ouarkziz crater is younger than the sedimentary rocks, as the rock layers had to be already present for the meteor to hit them. Likewise, a stream channel is visible cutting across the center of the structure, indicating that the channel formed after the impact had occurred. This Principal of Cross-Cutting Relationships, usually attributed to the 19th century geologist Charles Lyell, is a basic logic tool used by geologists to build relative sequence and history of events when investigating a region.” [27],[28],[29]

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Talemzane_crater

“Talemzane is an impact crater in Algeria, 40 km south-east of Hassi Delaa (a small city). One of four such craters in the country, Talemzane is classified as a simple crater. It has been designated by the 43rd Lunar and Planetary Science Conference to be a two-million- year-old, "true meteorite crater." Explored for the first time in 1928, studied in 1950 and 1988 by researchers from the universities of Oran (Algeria) and Nice (France). It is 1.75 km in diameter and the age is estimated to be less than three million years and is probably Pliocene. The name Maadna come from Arabic for "depression of ore.” [30],[31],[32],[33],[34],[35],[36]

Fig. 18 – The Talemzane Crater in DEM maps from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

In Mongolia

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tabun-Khara-Obo_crater

“Tabun-Khara-Obo is an impact crater in the Dornogovi Aimag (province) the south-east of Mongolia. The crater, which is exposed at the surface, is 1.3 km (0.81 mi) in diameter. The crater's rim rises some 20 to 30 metres (66 to 98 ft) above the crater bottom, but the bottom of crater is covered with up to 171 metres (561 ft) thick layer of lake deposits - a testimony that this crater in earlier times was filled with a lake. It has an estimated age of 150 ± 20 million years (Middle Jurassic to Early Cretaceous). The site was first identified as a probable impact crater in the 1960s, although confirmation of the hypothesis only occurred decades later. Drilling at the site in 2008 revealed rock features consistent with high-speed impacts such as those caused by meteorites.” [37],[38],[39],[40],[41].

Fig. 17 – The Tabun-Khara-Obo Crater in DEM map from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

Meteor Crater

Let us continue with an emblematic crater, from the list given by en.wikipedia.org: it is the Meteor Crater. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Meteor_Crater (see References therein)

“Meteor Crater, or Barringer Crater, is a meteorite impact crater about 37 mi (60 km) east of Flagstaff and 18 mi (29 km) west of Winslow in the desert of northern Arizona, United States. ... Because the United States Board on Geographic Names recognizes names of natural features derived from the nearest post office, the feature acquired the name of "Meteor Crater" from the nearby post office named Meteor. Meteor Crater lies at an elevation of 5,640 ft (1,719 m) above sea level. It is about 3,900 ft (1,200 m) in diameter, some 560 ft (170 m) deep, and is surrounded by a rim that rises 148 ft (45 m) above the surrounding plains. The center of the crater is filled with 690–790 ft (210–240 m) of rubble lying above crater bedrock. One of the interesting features of the crater is its squared-off outline, believed to be caused by existing regional jointing (cracks) in the strata at the impact site.”

Fig. 18 – The Meteor Crater in DEM map from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

Vredefort Crater

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vredefort_crater

“The Vredefort crater is the largest verified impact crater on Earth. It was 160–300 km (100–200 mi) across when it was formed; and what remains of it is in the present-day Free State province of South Africa. It is named after the town of Vredefort, which is near its centre. Although the crater itself has long since been eroded away, the remaining geological structures at its centre are known as the Vredefort Dome or Vredefort impact structure. The crater is calculated to be 2.023 billion years (± 4 million years) old, with impact being in the Paleoproterozoic Era. It is the second-oldest known crater on Earth, after Yarrabubba crater. In 2005, the Vredefort Dome was added to the list of UNESCO World Heritage Sites for its geologic interest.”

Fig. 19 – The Vredefort Crater in DEM map from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

In the Abstract of [42], 1961, about the Vredefort Ring structure of South Africa, the author is following the “heretical opinion of Boon, Albritton, and Daly” [43],[44], which is suggesting that the structure is a meteorite impact structure or “astrobleme.” “Using an impact velocity of 20 km/sec, it was found that an asteroid 2.3 km in diameter would provide the 6×10^{28} ergs (1.4 million megatons TNT-equivalent) needed to create the original crater 40 km across and roughly 16 km deep. An impact event adequately explains: (1) the apparent impulse direction which was radially outward from the center; (2) the shatter cones as shock-induced; (3) the bilateral symmetry as owing to an oblique impact; (4) the upturned and overtilted 16-km thick collar as the effect of radial forces spreading out from the explosion focus; (5) the pressure and thermal metamorphism of the sedimentary collar as shock wave-induced; (6) the intensive fracturing and microshearing of rock with little relative displacement as shock wave-induced; (7) the pseudotachylite as a “shock impactite” produced by overpressures in excess of 105 bars; and (8) the granophyre dikes as injected crater-lining “impactite.” The uplifted granite plug now filling the original crater was caused by a combination of elastic rebound and isostatic forces. It would seem that, at Vredefort, an impact event transpired equivalent to the formation of Copernicus or Tycho on the moon”. Other references are [45],[46],[47],[48],[49],[50].

Fig. 20 – The Manicouagan Crater in DEM map from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

Manicouagan Crater

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Manicouagan_Reservoir

“Manicouagan Reservoir (also Lake Manicouagan) is an annular lake in central Quebec, Canada, covering an area of 1,942 km² (750 sq mi). The lake island in its centre is known as René-Levasseur Island, and its highest point is Mount Babel. The structure was created 214 (±1) million years ago, in the Late Triassic, by the impact of a meteorite 5 km (3 mi) in diameter. The lake and island are clearly seen from space and are sometimes called the "eye of Quebec". The lake has a volume of 137.9 km³ (33.1 cu mi).” “It was suggested that the Manicouagan crater may have been part of a multiple impact event”. [51],[52],[52]

Fig. 21 – The Sedan Crater in DEM map from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

Sedan Crater

Let us add the Sedan Crater.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sedan_Crater

“Sedan Crater is the result of the Sedan nuclear test and is located within the Nevada Test Site, 12 miles (19 km) southwest of Groom Lake, Nevada (Area 51).”

Discussion

In the previously proposed examples, we have seen that the DEM method given in [3], implemented by the maps provided by <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>, can be very useful in the study of the elevation of crater-like structures. The colour map given by <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com> can have several layouts. It is possible to select OpenStreetMap, Open TopoMap, Carto / Light, Carto / Topo, CyclOSM, and Esri / Imagery (satellite imagery). By clicking on the maps it is also possible to display elevation of a specific location. Let us stress that, sometimes, colours can be greatly useful for the localization of craters in the maps. The following example illustrates this fact for a crater, in Arabia, mentioned in [54].

Fig. 22 – On the left, a crater in Arabia, mentioned in [54], coordinates $28^{\circ}38'46''\text{N}$, $37^{\circ}11'49''\text{E}$, as we can see in Google Earth Pro. On the right, the same crater in the colour DEM map from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>. Note that in the colour map, the crater is clearly visible due to its circular shape.

Using the Gallery of Google Earth Pro, we can find told “By: ekafeman, Date: 2009-04-19”, that the crater is named Al Madafi. The age is <360.0 Million Years. A detailed description is also provided. “Garwin and Blodgett (1986) described the structure based on stereo airphotos, Landsat images and a geologic map. The structure is located in flat-lying Ordovician and Devonian shales and sandstones of the Tabuk formation. Garwin and Blodgett (1986) ... proposed impact origin for the structure and estimated Cenozoic age based on the freshness of the rim. They saw no salt diapirs within 100s of km and saw young volcanics 45 km south of the structure. Grieve et al. (1988) noted upturned circular ridge with terraces and slumps on inner side, no central peak, different appearance from other volcanics in the area and noted that field inspection found no shock features. Grieve et al. (1988) listed an age <360 Ma. Listed by (McHone and Dietz, 1988)”. [55],[56],[57] In the following Figure, it is shown another crater from [54] (no information given by Google Earth Pro).

Fig. 23 – A crater in Arabia, mentioned in [54], coordinates 15°39'36"N, 44°42'49"E, in Google Earth Pro imagery In the upper panel, the same crater in the colour DEM map from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

In [54], I have also proposed the crater-like structures, here given in the Figures 24 and 25 (no information on a crater in the Gallery by Google Earth Pro).

Fig. 24 – A structure in Arabia, proposed in [54] as having a crater-like feature, at coordinates $21^{\circ}38'41''\text{N}$, $40^{\circ}23'59''\text{E}$, in Google Earth Pro. In the lower panel, the same crater in the colour DEM map from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>

Fig. 25 – Another structure in Arabia, proposed in [54] as having a crater-like feature, at coordinates $21^{\circ}55'17''\text{N}$, $38^{\circ}34'55''\text{E}$, Google Earth Pro. In the lower panel, the same crater in the colour DEM map from <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>. Again, colours are useful in increasing the visibility of the structure.

Let us consider again the region in Libya, given in the Figure 8. By a further inspection using <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com>, we can find other interesting places. Here one of them, in the following Figure.

Fig. 26 – A structure in Libya (coordinates $28^{\circ} 8'28.97''N$, $20^{\circ}23'46.83''E$). This crater is quite difficult to see in the Google Earth Pro images, however it is easy to find in the colour map by <https://it-ch.topographic-map.com> .

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